

Supplemental Fig. S4

Suppl. Fig. S4 (related to Fig. 4O-R). **False positive result in fluorescence imaging of islet cell microadenoma in human pancreas.** (A-C) Gross view and side-by-side display of fluorescence and transmitted light signals of microadenoma. The three images were derived from an optically cleared microadenoma (refractive index: 1.52). *A*: microadenoma alongside pancreatic lobules (red, blood vessels, CD31; green, lymphatic vessels, D2-40; white, nuclei, DAPI). *B*: enlarged fluorescence image of vasculature (blood and lymphatic vessels). *C*: overlay of transmitted light and nuclear signals. Adipocytes and blood clots (black spots) are prominently seen in *C* via in-depth transmitted light signals. Number 1-6 indicate the adipocytes (#1-2) and blood clots (#3-6) shown in both *B* and *C*. Alphabet a-f indicate the adipocytes and blood clots appear only in *C*. CD31 signals of *B* is presented in *D*. *B-D* examine the same microenvironment. (D, E) False positive result revealed by analysis of CD31 fluorescence signals of microadenoma. Relative signals intensity along the central line of *D* (0-2,000 pixels) is presented in *E*. Both CD31-labeled blood vessels and the blood clot-induced autofluorescence create local increases in the signal intensity (*E*). Number 4 in *E* indicates the autofluorescence caused by the blood clot #4 in panel *B-D*.